

BIOPHILIC DESIGN + POSITIVE DESIGN = VITAL DESIGN DESIGNING TO COMPREHENSIVELY SUPPORT USER WELLBEING

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ABSTRACT

Biophilic design leads to the development of places and objects that humans find beautiful and that generate a positive affect. Beautiful places and things endure because they are comforting, pleasing, and satisfying – aesthetically, emotionally, and, as required, functionally. Beauty is not just in the eyes of the beholders, and the development of beautiful places and objects can be informed by research in the social and physical sciences. Positive design leads to the creation of places and objects that directly enhance subjective wellbeing. They are tailored to the psychological profile, aspirations, and objectives of users. When designers incorporate principles of both biophilic and positive design into their projects, the vital design solutions generated resonate with users and are environmentally sustainable; they satisfy a wider range of user needs than either biophilic or positive design solutions. Field research will link biophilic design and positive design with vital design products that enhance user welfare.

KEYWORDS: *biophilic design, positive design, positive affect, subjective wellbeing, environmental/object design.*

INTRODUCTION

Developed societies must resolve several important challenges to ensure their continued viability. First, environmental responsibility is necessary to preserve quality of life, and, ultimately, life itself. Second, creating personally meaningful experiences for citizens is also imperative (Inglehart, 2000). As Hassenzahl, Eckoldt, Diefenbach, Laschke, Lenz, and Kim state, “While society changes its focus from ‘well-fare’ to ‘wellbeing’, design becomes increasingly interested in the question of whether it can design for happiness” (2013, p.21). Biophilic design directly supports resolution of the first challenge and positive design the second by enhancing subjective wellbeing (Kellert, 2012; Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). When biophilic design and positive design are consciously combined, in a process that can be categorized as vital design, the resulting design products are both meaningful and sustainable, and society as a whole, as well as individuals and smaller groups, benefit because critical needs at all levels of scale are recognized and satisfied. User needs from each step of Maslow’s hierarchy, from physiological to security to social to self esteem to self-actualization (Koltko-Rivera, 2006) can be fully satisfied via vital design.

Both biophilic design and positive design can generate positive affect (Kellert, 2008; Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013) and it is therefore logical that vital design can do so also. Positive affect has been linked to broadened thinking/attention and thought-action repertoires, when compared to neutral or negative state processing (Fredrickson & Branigan, 2005). In general, positive affect has been positively related to: improved creative performance and increased innovation (Isen, Johnson, Mertz, & Robinson, 1985); improved problem solving and decision making (Isen, 2001); more flexible, thorough, and efficient thinking on topics meaningful or interesting to the thinker (Isen, 2001); strategic thinking (Loken, 2006); constructive and cooperative bargaining, increased generosity, social responsibility, helping and interpersonal understanding (Isen, 2001); constructive suggestions (George & Brief, 1992); avoidance of real and meaningful risk (Isen, Johnson, Mertz, & Robinson, 1985); and improved self-knowledge (Fredrickson, 2001). Positive emotions can help build durable personal resources such as physical skills or health, social resources such as friendships and networks, intellectual resources such as knowledge, and psychological resources such as optimism (Fredrickson & Branigan, 2005).

BIOPHILIC DESIGN

Kellert defines biophilia as “the inherent inclination to affiliate with the natural world instrumental to people’s physical and mental health, productivity, and wellbeing”, while biophilicly designed structures reflect the essential qualities of spaces found in nature, without necessarily being precise replications of natural places (Kellert, 2012, p. xii). Biophilicly designed areas “are designed in ways that foster people’s physical and mental health through providing positive connections to nature in a context of ecological and cultural meaning” (Kellert, 2012, p. 158).

Denis Dutton delineated the link between beauty and biophilic design (2009). His work makes it clear that biophilic design leads to the development of spaces and objects that humans consider beautiful, regardless of their culture of origin. Dutton traces the apparently universal associations between biophilic design and beauty to the Pleistocene environments in which humans reached roughly their current state of evolutionary development, physically and socially. Dutton’s position is that we consider certain aspects of nature beautiful today because the same elements, during the Pleistocene era, supported our survival; for example, by helping us escape from predators.

Dutton details how across the planet people find the same sort of landscapes beautiful and illustrates his claim by referring to the Hudson River school of painting. These paintings and locations share certain attributes. They have a view out over stretches of grassy fields with occasional groups of trees (preferably with forks near the ground). Water is either directly in view or inferred in the distances and a trail we could walk, because it is a path or shoreline or riverbank, invites us to enter the scene and move through it among other animals and birds. Similar examples are provided of biophilic objects, such as ancient ax heads, although research has focused on biophilicly designed spaces. Those aspects of nature found beautiful have been studied, and their underlying “design principles” identified. Those design principles form the basis of biophilic design and will be enumerated in the paragraphs that follow.

When spaces or objects are developed using biophilic design principles, they are preferred to non-biophilic alternatives and people feel very comfortable in them or while using them (Kellert, 2012). As a result, their users generally think broadly, with all of the benefits noted above. Being in a beautiful, biophilicly designed space enhances positive affect (Kellert, 2012), while beautiful objects are perceived to work better, be easier to work with, and more straightforward to figure out (Fogg, Soohoo, Anielson, Marable, Stanford, & Tauber, 2003). Beauty, in short, is functional as well as preferred.

Kellert directly links biophilic design and the experience of beauty with environmentally sustainable behavior (2012, p.162). As he states:

Ultimately, low-impact design fails to achieve its goal of sustainability, because it falls short of nurturing the physical and mental benefits that create the emotional and

intellectual attachment that motivates people to be good stewards of their constructions and to retain them over the long term... As the architect James Wines suggested: ‘People will never want to keep an aesthetically inferior building around, no matter how well stocked with cutting edge thermal glass, photovoltaic cells, recycled materials, and zero-emissions carpeting’.

Hosey makes a similar point, “As studies show, we form positive associations with things we consider beautiful, we are more likely to become emotionally attached, giving them pet names, for instance. We personalize things we care about... people generally consider attractive products more functional than they do unsightly ones and therefore are more apt to use them. We prefer using things that look better, even if they aren’t inherently easier to use. Consider the ramifications—if an object is more likely to be used, it’s more likely to continue being used. Who throws out a thing they find functional, beautiful, and valuable all at once? A more attractive design discourages us from abandoning it: if we want it, we won’t waste it” (2012, p. 7). In addition, “we also take better care of such [attractive] environments, which tend to have less litter, waste, and vandalism” (2012, p. 26).

Kellert identifies signature principles of biophilic design (2008). They include:

- Using natural elements, from materials to sunlight and fresh air to plants.
- Including natural shapes, generally curvilinear.
- Creating the same sort of sensory experiences found in nature by, for example, actively considering the full range of sensations that people will experience, e.g., place/product related scents, textures touched, etc. Ideally, these should vary with time, as experiences in nature are different at various times of the day and year, or in response to more random events, such as a thunderstorm. Some materials change over longer periods of time, for example, as they age and develop a patina.
- Developing links between spaces/objects being designed and the physical and cultural environments where they will be used.
- Utilizing visual fractals with specific parameters, as outlined in a paragraph to follow.
- Integrating humans in ways that make them feel safe and confident. We feel secure when we’re not concerned about being approached from the rear without our knowledge and when we can survey the world around us from a protected position (this is known as having “prospect and refuge”), for example.
- Generating the same experience of spaciousness found in natural settings while clearly delineating individual territories (when spaces are designed).

Heerwagen and Gregory (2008) build on the basic tenets of biophilic design presented by Kellert (2008). They propose creating ‘a new palette for design’ that has, in addition to the biophilic elements identified by Kellert:

- Gentle, repetitive, rhythmic motion, like that of grasses in a meadow moving in a slight breeze.
- Pleasant but not totally predictable encounters/experiences. These might be, for example, at a variety of scales, one at standing height and another when people are seated and explore an object at closer range. Building ornamentation can vary in appearance as light illuminates it in different ways, leading to unexpected, but pleasant, experiences. Unanticipated positive experiences are rewards for sensory exploration.
- Flexible use options. When we're outside in natural settings, we have multiple possibilities for what to do next, and spaces and objects can also support flexibility, spontaneity, and a range of activities. Flexibility is closely related to 'freeness' in an environment and strategically placed sight lines that provide expansive views as well as openable windows that can be opened promote 'freeness'.

Judith Heerwagen (2009) discusses several additional attributes of biophilic design. She proposes using simulated (via photographs or other means) natural elements (i.e., views and plants), when real ones are not an option. She also recommends creating spaces/objects that are as complex visually, acoustically, etc., as natural ones to optimize the level of sensory inputs received by people.

Joye (2007) finds that biophilic design enhance humans' emotional and cognitive performance, and discusses additional attributes of biophilic architectural/interior design, recommending:

- Varying architectural topography.
- Including water features, or when possible, small fires in spaces developed.
- Repeating design elements through patterns in tiling, mosaics, stained glass, and oriental carpets.
- Bending a hallway or corridor slightly, so that there is some mystery surrounding what may lie around the corner. Too much mystery can be confusing, but levels of mystery can be moderated by views to the outside or a more regular building shape.

Joye notes that many different styles of popular architecture display details at different scales, mimicking to some extent fractal patterns.

Research, only some of which can be presented here, supports the biophilic design recommendations made by Kellert, Heerwagen, Joye, and others and highlights their positive implications for mood and the related matters of preference and performance.

- In a comprehensive assessment of the literature, Browning and his team found that biophilic architectural/interior design is linked to greater professional productivity, enhanced mental health and wellbeing, and better financial performance at stores and corporations; improved health of hospital patients; and expedited learning rates for students (Browning et al., 2012).

- Research consistently finds that when people experience visual or acoustic fractal patterns similar to those found in nature they become more relaxed and their mood improves (Wise, 2002). In all fractals, the components of a pattern appear at various magnifications within the same overall unit. For example, the smallest visible components of ferns have the same basic form as entire fern leaves. As Wise reports, the experience of natural fractals has been shown to speed recovery from surgery and to increase office worker productivity. Research in knowledge-worker offices has found that the use of visible natural fractals in an environment can improve memory while reducing stress and keeping cognitive performance from deteriorating over time (Wise, 2002). Warmuth and Joseph have found that the sound of indoor waterfalls, which is a natural acoustic fractal, significantly reduces the systolic blood pressure of people with dementia (2008). Higher levels of systolic blood pressure speeds cognitive decline. A literature review revealed that humans seem to prefer and are most comfortable when fractal patterns have values of 1.3 to 1.5, and people judge these fractals most aesthetically pleasing (Joye, 2007). These are the same values observed in fractals found in biophilic environments (Wise & Hazzard, 2002).
- The optimal scale of visual patterns for wallpapers, etc., seems to be one in which it's relatively easy to pick out potentially dangerous elements; smaller scale ones are preferred to larger (Rodemann, 1999).
- Humans register their highest levels of environmental satisfaction—and higher levels of environmental satisfaction have been linked to superior professional performance—in places with moderate visual complexity and similarly prefer to look at scene/artwork with moderate visual complexity (Kaplan, 1987; Forsythe, Nadal, Sheehy, Cela-Conde & Sawey, 2011). It is easy to spot predators against such patterns (Wise & Hazzard, 2002).
- Seeing wood grain is a natural de-stressor (Fell, 2010). This information is particularly important because wooden objects and finishes can be used in any sort of space (e.g., schools, hospitals, offices)—for example ones without views of nature, or ones that cannot support plants.
- Symmetrical stimuli (objects, patterns, etc.) are preferred and generally found to be beautiful, and in nature healthy living things are generally symmetrical (Lindell & Mueller, 2011; Chen, Wu, & Wu, 2011). Open and symmetrical spaces are categorized as more beautiful than any others (Ellard, 2009).
- Sunlight varies in color through the course of any day, and Knoop has identified benefits of varying the colors of artificial light used inside during the day (2007). Warm light is best when people prefer to relax and cooler light is better when people need to be alert. Sunlight at noon is a cooler color and at sunset is a warmer color.
- When we don't have access to daylight, which not only changes in color but also in intensity during the day, we become tense and under-stimulated (Veitch & Galasiu, 2012).

- Natural objects tend to be more curvilinear and research has shown that people prefer objects that are curved and feel calmer, in better moods, and more comfortable in spaces where curved elements predominate (Bar & Neta, 2007; Dazkir & Read, 2012; Vartanian et al., 2013).
- When investigating preferred seats in restaurants, Robson learned that the locations where people experience the most positive moods are those where there is something significant, such as a wall, column, partition, or large plant, for example, behind the seated patron, which impedes the approach of potentially troublesome others (2008).
- While studying preferred design for sleeping areas, Sporre and Stich found that people prefer to sleep in a location from which they can see the entrance to the space where they're sleeping and are as far as possible from that door (2010). They also want their bed to be positioned so that it is hidden from view when the door to their sleeping area is opened.
- In urban spaces, bodies of water are perceived to be more beautiful if they are wider and if there is vegetation along their banks (Steinwender, Gundacker, & Wittmann, 2008). Artificial (hard) bank modifications seem to make bodies of water less attractive.
- Ulrich and Gilpin (2003) have determined that figurative art in healthcare settings with the following attributes enhances the likelihood of healing: green landscapes (or flowers in gardens) with an open foreground; clusters of broad canopy trees; and calm, non-threatening water elements. Abstract images should be avoided or there will be negative effects on healing. Images of threatening situations (such as extreme weather or dangerous animals) also have a deleterious effect on healing.

Biophilic design has been linked to enhanced mood, which has desirable implications for emotional, cognitive, and social performance, as detailed above. Biophilic design also has been tied to the creation of spaces and objects that are judged beautiful and that are preferred.

POSITIVE DESIGN

Desmet and Pohlmeier (2013, p. 8-9) define: “‘positive design’ as an umbrella term for all forms of design, design research and design intention in which explicit attention is paid to the effects of design on the subjective well-being of individuals and communities.... Positive design initiatives deliberately intend to increase people’s subjective well-being and, hence, increase an enduring appreciation of their lives. It is important to note that this target is the explicit central objective at the outset of a positive design process, not simply a fortunate side effect of a design.” Desmet and Pohlmeier also acknowledge that, “positive design does not deny the place of loss, failure, and negative emotions in the richness of life experiences” (2013, p. 16). Its primary purpose is to increase the likelihood that humans flourish.

Positive design, as described by Desmet and Pohlmeier, has three major components: pleasure, personal significance, and virtue (2013). When all three are present users are more likely to flourish (although all need not be present to the same degree for the effect to be found). Each element must be tailored to the psychological profile, aspirations, and objectives of anticipated users to promote flourishing.

- Pleasurable design enhances happiness at the moment of experience. This positive design objective is consistent with those of biophilic design, although biophilic design supports user comfort and security at a fundamental level and is linked only peripherally to instantaneous pleasure.
- Design for personal significance “addresses happiness that comes from a sense of personal meaning. The focus is not on momentary affect, but on one’s personal (long- or short-term) goals and aspirations” (p. 9).
- Design for virtue; “for example, eyeglasses can facilitate reading and learning (i.e., the virtues of knowledge and wisdom)” (p. 9). Both goals and virtue are achieved through individual effort. Both designing for personal significance and designing for virtue are not recognized by biophilic design, although biophilic design is environmentally responsible.

Augustin has similarly described design that enhances well-being as having five attributes (2009). It

- Comforts by providing desirable and pleasant sensory experiences.
- Communicates by sending desired messages about users to others as well as to themselves and, in general, supports social interaction.
- Complies by helping users achieve their performance objectives.
- Challenges by facilitating the development of users in ways they find meaningful.
- Continues by remaining available to users over an extended period of time, which is pleasurable and comforting.

Jordan (2000) has designated four types of pleasure that can be derived from products (drawing on the work of Lionel Tiger), and these align with the tenets of positive design as described by Desmet and Pohlmeier (2013). The evidence Jordan presents confirming the four types of pleasure he delineates validates the positive design approach. The types of pleasure discussed by Jordan are:

- Physio-pleasure – “pleasures derived from the sensory organs” (p. 13).
- Socio-pleasure – “derived from relationships with others”, both those known to the user and ‘society as a whole’ (p. 13).
- Psycho-pleasure – “pertains to people’s cognitive and emotional reactions... this might include issues relating to the cognitive demands of using the product and the emotional reactions engendered through experiencing the product” (p. 14).

- Ideo-pleasure – “pertains to people’s values.... For example, a product made from bio-degradable materials might be seen as embodying the value of environmental responsibility. This, then, would be a potential source of ideo-pleasure to those who are particularly concerned about environmental issues” (p. 14).

Positive design has a strong foundation in both practice and theory, as described above. It is more tightly linked to individual experiences with spaces and objects, and less to generalized ones, than biophilic design.

BIOPHILIC DESIGN, POSITIVE DESIGN, VITAL DESIGN

When biophilic design and positive design principles are simultaneously applied, the design products generated provide psychological support to users at multiple levels and vital design ensues. Biophilic design sustains users by focusing on their continuing requirements for physical comfort and safety. While positive design attends to momentary satisfaction of psychological needs at multiple levels of Maslow’s hierarchy of needs (Koltko-Rivera, 2006), it excels at supporting those at a higher level, by considering personal meaning and virtue, for example. Vital design therefore satisfies user needs at each step of Maslow’s pyramid, both instantaneously and continuously; something neither biophilic design, positive design, nor design in general does well.

A program spontaneously undertaken by an employer, without input from the researcher, illustrates how vitally designed spaces can develop, and their value to users. Forty workers at an advertising agency in North America were each given \$300 by their employer for enhancements to their workplace cubicles. The changes that these naïve designers made were consistent with vital design. The researcher interviewed these workers after they modified their workplaces (the only access acceptable to the employing organization was via interviews) and the data collected indicated that after modifying the design of their workspaces, the workers felt more committed to their employer organization than they had beforehand. Study participants also felt that after modifying their workspaces they enjoyed their time at work more and spent more time in their workplace than they had previously. Finally, they believed that they performed their professional responsibilities better in the modified workspaces than in the original ones. These perceived changes in job performance, etc., are consistent with more positive affect and higher levels of subjective wellbeing (see the first section of this paper for more information on mood, wellbeing, and performance, etc.). Also, consistent with biophilic design-related research, none of the individuals interviewed wished to make any significant changes to the design of their workspaces even six months after the cubicles were modified. All planned changes were minor, for example, re-arranging furniture already brought to the workspace from home.

All of the workers who had the opportunity to enhance their workspaces chose to do so. In addition, they were all active-

ly involved in the design and implementation process. This active control over their experiences no doubt contributed to their apparent increased happiness: “Through the deliberate and active engagement with the world, people can—at least to some degree—take control over their experiences and, thus, make themselves more (or less) happy” (Hassenzahl et al., 2013, p. 21).

Many of the workspace enhancements were clearly biophilic. For example, living plants were popular additions to workplaces as were plant and other natural materials. Workers often re-oriented their desks/seats to face the entrance to cubicles. When this was not possible for structural reasons, several employees placed large mirrors so that they had excellent views of the entrance to their cubicles. These modifications created true or pseudo ‘protected back’ positions. Several individuals hung objects overhead that moved gently in currents created by the air conditioning system. Cubicle re-designs were generally multi-sensory and invited exploration. Spaces developed also had many curved elements and could often be used in a variety of ways (e.g., cubicles now contained reconfigurable work areas).

Also in line with biophilic design principles, individuals created clearly delineated territories that they alone could claim. Boundaries were established via several methods, including the addition of rugs that indicated the extent of floor space belonging to a particular individual as well as the addition of a plaster-like material to the inside surfaces of some cubicle walls to make the cubicles themselves seem more substantial. Some workers added doors—swinging on hinges or made from bead curtains—to their cubicles. One enterprising individual added a doorbell to their cubicle as a way to signal availability—if she did not answer the doorbell, she was not available for discussion. Others indicated their availability via flag-based signal systems. In one case, a territory was established via a scent; the amount of scent dispensed into the air by a finely tuned mechanical system spread to the edge of a cubicle territory and no further.

Each cubicle, after its transformation, contained elements that clearly linked it to a single individual. Often the style/assortment of objects and decorative motifs used to customize the cubicle were described as similar to those found in the cubicle owner’s living room at home. As the work of Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton has shown, residents use the design of their living rooms to signal important qualities of their self to themselves and others (1981). Personalizing elements included an extensive collection of cartoon figurines, personal photographs, and artwork created by relatives, for example.

Many of the design elements, such as the scents and plants added to spaces, were presented as ways to enhance the momentary experience of being in a place, which is consistent with positive design.

Most of the workplace enhancements that the users developed were introduced to achieve workplace performance goals and to augment virtue by increasing wisdom/knowledge/skill. For example, one individual eliminated the desk

from his cubicle so that he could sit on the floor and work because he felt that he thought more clearly and did better work when seated cross-legged on the floor than he did while seated in a traditional desk-type chair. Other goals were more immediate and mercenary, for example, selling paintings done by a son.

Some of the modifications made to the work environments were clearly and singly linked to being virtuous. For example, one employee developed displays to facilitate bonding with African tribes people and self-identified as a benevolent world citizen. Other space enhancements were tied to religion/spirituality, such as large Christian crosses. Certain changes related to the virtue of bonding with colleagues; most of the re-fashioned cubicles had candy dishes containing sweets for visitors.

Some of the cubicle modifications focused on one or two of the three positive design components, but none of the changes made seemed to have negative repercussions for the attainment of components not specifically focused upon. Consistent with positive design, each worker created a space that they enjoyed being in and from which they could improve their world, at multiple levels.

Employees of the North American advertising agency that is the subject of this field of research were not trained architects or interior designers. They modified their workspaces, applying principles of both biophilic design and positive design, and created spaces that were environmentally sustainable. These spaces were also personally meaningful and consistent with efforts to achieve personal goals and live virtuous lives. The spaces created are vital areas, supporting the present and future wellbeing of both their users and their society.

CONCLUSION

Biophilic design and positive design enhance positive affect and subjective wellbeing, which, as detailed in the first section of this paper, has personal and societal benefits. Biophilic design leads to the development of beautiful objects/spaces and environmentally responsible lifestyles. These objects/spaces may not, however, be personally meaningful and enrich individual lives. Positive design leads to pleasurable experiences that resonate with individual goals and supports being virtuous in ways that are significant to users, but may not provide the long-term comfort of biophilically designed objects/spaces. In addition, virtues championed may not be related to environmentally responsible behavior. Neither biophilic design nor positive design alone leads to the creation of places/objects that fully satisfy individual and societal needs on a continuing basis and at all levels of Maslow's hierarchy of needs (Koltko-Rivera, 2006). Biophilic design and positive design can therefore stimulate and enhance each other and when applied together encourage subjective wellbeing. Applying both approaches to design simultaneously leads to vital design products that enrich individual and societal wellbeing.

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